

**INVESTMENT ATTRACTION AS ONE
FROM THE ACTIVITIES OF THE REAL SECTOR**

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Abstract. The article covers the relevance of innovative ideas for the improvement of the standard of living and well-being of the population, the development of the economy, the factors of the formation of the investment environment in our country, and the effective regional investment policy in the real sector of the economy of Uzbekistan.

Key words: innovative development, investment, investment climate, regional, economy, attractive conditions.

Expanded reproduction of material values, ensuring the growth of national income, is a necessary condition for ensuring economic growth, the development of society as a whole and individual business entities. Currently, there is an increasing need to attract long-term investments in order to purchase the latest equipment and introduce technological innovations. Successful solution of socio-economic problems, the introduction of new industrial and financial technologies, the development of investment infrastructure, the growth of intellectual potential, the production of export-oriented, import-substituting products and the accumulation of foreign exchange reserves in the country largely remain dependent on the level of innovative activity.

The quality, relevance and level of innovative ideas are increasing every day. It should be noted that much attention is paid to the relevance of research and development and innovative technologies. When implementing innovative projects, special attention should be paid to the development of import-substituting raw materials and materials. The goal is to involve our scientists in the creation of developments that will serve the development of the industry.

All of the above led to the creation in our country of the Ministry of Innovative Development, the Decree on the formation of which was signed by the President of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev on November 29, 2017. This document defines the main directions of the country's innovative development. The Decree acknowledges that accelerated innovative development in Uzbekistan is hampered by a number of systemic problems, as well as insufficient use of existing opportunities and potential. One of these problems is the low level of cooperation with foreign and international organizations. [1] Along with

this, the main directions of innovative development of the regions of Uzbekistan are outlined: wide attraction of investments in the development and implementation of innovative ideas and technologies; formation of a modern infrastructure for the development of science and innovation, capable of providing the necessary conditions for the sustainable growth of the socio-economic potential of the territories, as well as improving the standard of living and welfare of the population; creation of effective mechanisms for promoting and implementing promising domestic achievements in research and innovation, including the organization of scientific and experimental specialized laboratories, high-tech centers, technology parks and other structures, including with the participation of foreign investors; creation of favorable conditions for talented youth; accelerated introduction of modern information and communication, industrial and other innovative technologies that ensure the comprehensive development of the sectors of the real sector of the economy; promotion of innovative ideas, developments and technologies in the agricultural sector, including new breeding varieties of agricultural crops that contribute to increasing the efficiency of production and the export potential of agricultural producers, strengthening the country's food security, etc.

The following factors influence the investment climate of the country [2]:

- 1) administrative and legal conditions (system of legislation, compliance with guarantees of property rights and protection of the rights of participants in the investment project, the degree of enforcement of laws, etc.);
- 2) economic situation (tax system, market potential, values of such key macroeconomic indicators as GDP, inflation rate, exchange rate stability, competitive environment, resource potential, etc.);
- 3) political situation (legitimate power, development of democratic institutions, civil society, predictability of foreign policy, etc.);
- 4) state and development of infrastructure (accessibility of public services, availability and objectivity of information, development of infrastructure, etc.);
- 5) development of industry (leading industries, the level of depreciation of the fixed capital of industrial enterprises, conducting work in the field of creating high technologies - the presence of specialized research centers, testing laboratories, etc.);
- 6) social sphere (standard of living of the population, including the proportion of the poor, the unemployment rate, the level, quality and accessibility of education, the demographic situation, etc.);

7) geographical location, state of ecology (territorial location, state of the environment, etc.).

The investment climate, respectively, is determined mainly by factors and conditions that are the result of the ongoing state policy in the field of economics, law, and external relations of the state.

During the years of independence, a favorable investment climate has been created in Uzbekistan, a wide system of legal guarantees and benefits for foreign investors, a system of measures has been developed to stimulate the activities of enterprises with foreign investments. [3]

The investment legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan has absorbed the main provisions of international investment law, in particular, provisions on guaranteeing the rights of foreign investors, providing certain preferences for investors, and others. The Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Foreign Investments”, “On Investment Activities”, “On Guarantees and Measures to Protect the Rights of Foreign Investors”, a number of legal acts adopted in the form of decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and government decrees are the basis of legal regulation in the field of attracting foreign investments in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Given the fact that the investment climate affects almost all areas of the country's activities, the range of reforms covered all areas, including economic, institutional, educational, healthcare, agriculture, water supply, energy, transport and others.

The President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev initiated the 1st Tashkent International Investment Forum, which started on March 24, 2022. The head of state spoke about the conditions created for investors: free currency conversion, removal of restrictions on the repatriation of profits, obtaining international credit ratings and issuing bonds by companies, visa-free regime with 90 countries, simplified visa regime with 60 states and others.

First of all, we eliminated all the factors that previously prevented investors from entering the market of Uzbekistan and their free activity and began to create favorable conditions for entrepreneurship,” said Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his speech. [4]

The President said that the annual volume of foreign investments has grown 3.5 times over the past five years, and their amount during this time has reached \$25 billion. At the expense of these funds, 59 thousand investment projects were implemented and 2.5 million jobs were created. The volume of gold and foreign exchange reserves has grown from 27 billion to 35 billion dollars, and over the

next five years it is planned to increase gross domestic product to 100 billion dollars, annual exports to 30 billion dollars.

Recognizing that the pandemic and other crises of recent years make it necessary to look for non-standard solutions, the president assured that Uzbekistan will continue to make efforts to create "the most convenient and attractive conditions for investors". [4] Noting the importance of digitalization, "green" technologies and innovations for development in all areas of business at the present stage, he invited investors for practical cooperation: "Ensuring your success in our country is guaranteed by the President and Government of Uzbekistan" [4].

Back in 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted that "... Investments must be targeted, cost-effective. Funds must be directed depending on the potential of the districts, on what enterprises the region needs" [5]. Indeed, each region should get a real opportunity to maximize the existing potential for its development and growth in the well-being of the population. In accordance with this, an effective regional investment policy should be implemented in the republic, which contributes to equalizing the economic conditions for independent regional management and decentralization of management. [6]

In conclusion, it should be noted that the choice of regional development models is of particular importance depending on the strategic goals set and the functional characteristics of the models used. Efficient use of the natural and economic potential of the region equally requires the implementation of both oriented and projected models of local growth.

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